

ting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised.

3-(5-Arylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridines (7): Appropriate 4-aryl-1-[(2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-yl)carbonyl]-3-thiosemicarbazide (6; 0.1 mol) was dissolved/suspended in ethanol (25 ml) and 4*N* NaOH (5 ml) was added to it with cooling and shaking. To resulting the clear solution, iodine in 5% potassium iodide solution was added gradually with stirring till the colour of iodine persisted at room temperature. The contents were then refluxed on a water-bath and more iodine solution was added till permanent tinge of excess iodine remained. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water, and the precipitated solid was filtered off, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

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Some New Sulphides from 4-Bromomethylcarbostyryl

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HETEROARYL and diheteroaryl sulphides containing benzimidazole¹ and coumarin² moieties are useful as fungicides and antimicrobials. Further, 1-dialkylaminoalkyl benzimidazolyl-2-sulphides³ and 4-substituted-carbostyryls⁴ exhibit wide

ranging pharmacological properties⁴. In view of the above observations, this paper reports the synthesis, spectral and pharmacological properties of a variety of sulphides incorporating benzimidazole, coumarin and carbostyryl moieties (Scheme 1).

4-Bromomethylcarbostyryl⁵ (1) reacted with 2-mercaptobenzimidazole⁶ in alcohol in presence of potassium hydroxide to give the sulphide (2) which underwent Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and secondary amines to give the Mannich bases (3). Reaction of 1 with thiourea in ethanol afforded 4-mercaptomethylcarbostyryl (4) which was condensed with different 4-bromomethylcoumarins⁷ to get the diheteroaryl sulphides (5). The arylsulphide (6) was synthesised by the reaction of thio-phenol with 1.

Mass spectrum of 5a showed the molecular ion M^+ at m/e 363 (20%) and this was confirmed by the (M+H) ion at 364 (100%) from the chemical ionisation spectrum.

The composition (base peak at m/e 159) was found to be $C_{10}H_7O_2$. A plausible route for this fragmentation is the β -cleavage giving rise to the even electron ions (II) and (III) with the concomitant expulsion of CH_2S . Both these ions can expel a molecule of CO to give ring contracted benzofuran(IV) and indole(V) ions respectively which is characteristic of coumarin⁸ and carbostyryl⁹ systems. Heterolytic fission of one of the C-S bonds results in the α -cleavage giving rise to even electron ions (VI) and (VII) respectively. Another probable route of fragmentation of (I) is by H-transfer similar to dibenzylsulphide¹⁰ giving rise to odd electron ions (VIII) and (IX) respectively. The thioaldehyde ion (IX) can expel a molecule of CS to end up in ion (XI) of high intensity. The 4,6-dimethylcoumarin ion (VIII) shows expulsion of CO giving rise to the dimethylbenzofuran ion (X) (Scheme 2).

Biological activity: Analgesic activity of the sulphide (2) and Mannich bases (3) was evaluated by the Eddy's hot-plate method¹¹ employing morphine sulphate as standard at a dose level of 100 mg/kg in albino mice. The reaction time was measured periodically up to 8 h. The sulphide (2) had very little effect, and among the Mannich bases 3b and 3e retained the activity at the end of 8th hour. Both these compounds showed the maximum analgesic response at the end of 2nd and 4th hour respectively.

4-Mercaptomethylcarbostyryl (4) and the sulphides (5) were screened for their antimicrobial activity against *A. niger*, *C. albicans*, *R. arrhizus* and *R. nigricans*. The free thiol inhibited the growth of all the species at a concentration of 100 μ g ml⁻¹ while the sulphides (5) were found inactive.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer instrument, ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as

Scheme 1

Reaction of 2 with secondary amines and formaldehyde. General method: A mixture of 2 (0.001 mol), a secondary amine (0.001 mol) and formalin (37%; 0.006 mol) in ethanol was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and left overnight to obtain the crystals of the Mannich bases (3; Table 1).

Scheme 2

internal standard, and mass spectra on a Mat CH-7 instrument.

4-(2'-S-Benzimidazolyl)mercaptomethylcarbostryl (2): To a suspension of 4-bromomethylcarbostryl (1; 0.004 mol) and 2-mercaptobenzimidazole (0.004 mol) in ethanol (20 ml), was added KOH (0.004 mol). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h and then cooled. After cooling, the separated solid was washed with excess of water and crystallised from acetic acid, (2; 80%), m.p. 232° (Found: C, 66.2; H, 4.10; N, 13.42. C₁₇H₁₃N₃OS requires: C, 66.45; H, 4.23; N, 13.68%; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (DMSO-d₆) 4.8 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 6.6. (1H, s, C₃-H, carbostryl) and 7.0–8.2 (8H, m, ArH).

4-Mercaptomethylcarbostryl (4): A mixture of 1 (0.004 mol) and thiourea (0.004 mol) was stirred in ethanol-ether (1 : 1, v/v) mixture at room temperature for 2 h, and then refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h and left overnight. The separated solid was washed with excess of water, dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%; 15 ml), reprecipitated by adding HCl and recrystallised from acetic acid, (4; 75%), m.p. 189° (Found: C, 62.7; H, 4.5; N, 7.20. C₁₀H₉NOS requires: C, 62.8; H, 4.7; N, 7.33%; ν_{max} (KBr) 2 520 (SH), 1 660 (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 1.6 (1H, br, SH exchangeable), 3.75 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, S-CH₂), 6.45 (1H, s, C₃-H, carbostryl) and 6.7–7.5 (4H, m, ArH).

4-(4'-S-Coumarinomethyl)mercaptomethyl carbostryls (5): A mixture of 4 (0.002 mol), 4-bromomethylcoumarin (0.002 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.002 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. After cooling the separated solid was filtered and treated with dilute HCl. The residual solid was filtered and washed with excess of water. The filtrate was concentrated and diluted with water to get the second crop. All the compounds were crystallised from acetic acid (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 5*

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	ν_{\max} (KBr) cm^{-1}	$\delta(\text{CCl}_4/\text{DMSO}-d_6)$
3a	Piperidino	80	201	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	1 615 (C=N), 1 680 (C=O)	1.4 (6H, s, CH_2-C), 2.8 (4H, s, CH_2-N), 4.4 (2H, s, C_3-H), 4.6 (2H, s, CH_2-S), 6.35 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.7–7.5 (8H, m, ArH)
3b	Morpholino	80	232	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$	1 610 (C=N), 1 655 (C=O)	δ 3.4 (4H, s, N- CH_2), 4.5 (2H, s, N- CH_2-N), 4.6 (2H, s, CH_2S), 6.4 (1H, s, C_3-H)
3c	Dimethylamino	60	212	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	1 620 (C=N), 1 680 (C=O)	δ 4.6 (2H, s, CH_2-S), 5.15 (2H, s, N- CH_2-N), 6.4 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.7–7.5 (8H, m, ArH)
3d	N-Methylanilino	75	182	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	1 605 (C=N), 1 660 (C=O)	2.9 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 4.65 (2H, s, CH_2-S), 5.35 (2H, s, N- CH_2-N), 6.4 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.8–7.5 (13H, m, ArH)
3e	Pyrrolidino	70	185	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	1 610 (C=N), 1 670 (C=O)	—
5a	6- CH_3	70	265	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$	1 670 (lactum), 1 720 (lactone)	—
5b	7- CH_3	70	282	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$	1 670, 1 730	—
5c	6- OCH_3	65	252	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4\text{S}$	1 670, 1 720	—
5d	7- OCH_3	60	246	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4\text{S}$	1 665, 1 725	—
5e	5,6-Benzo	65	263	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$	1 660, 1 720	—

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses. δ N- CH_3 and O- CH_3 protons were found to merge in the DMSO peak.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Screening of New *s*-Triazolothiadiazines

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THE antiparasitic activities of *s*-triazoles are well-known^{1,2}. In continuation of our studies³ on the synthesis of *s*-triazolothiadiazines, a number of new 3-substituted-6,7-diaryl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]-thiadiazines (2) have been prepared by condensing the appropriate 3-substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (1) with α -bromodeoxybenzoins⁴ following the reported procedure³. The structures of the compounds were based on elemental analysis, ir, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data. Results of their antimicrobial screening have also been reported.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer. The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra were recorded on Varian VXR-300s (300 MHz) and Bruker WH-270 (67.89 MHz) FTNMR spectrometers respectively using CDCl_3 as the solvent. The following 3-aryloxymethyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-(4*H*)-1,2,4-triazoles (1; R=Ar-O CH_2) were prepared⁴. 3-Phenoxymethyl (Ar=C₆H₅), m.p. 134°; 3-*p*-toloxymethyl (Ar=*p*-CH₃-C₆H₄), m.p. 190°;